

DOES INFLATION KILL? AN EXPOSURE TO INFLATION AND UNDER-FIVE MORTALITY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Does inflation kill? This paper investigated empirically the effect of inflation on under-five mortality in Nigeria using annual time series covering a period of 35 years, which is between 1990 and 2024. The study used Under-5 Mortality Rate (UFM) as the dependent variable whereas Inflation (INF), Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC), Government Expenditure on Health (GEH), and Unemployment (UNEMP) were used as the independent variables. Data were collected from secondary sources and analyzed using descriptive statistics, unit root test, and Co-integration and ECM techniques. The results of the ECM shows that Inflation (INF) increases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM); GDP per capita (GDPPC) reduces Under-5 Mortality Rate (UFM); Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) increases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM); Unemployment (UNEMP) has no significant effect on Under-5 Mortality Rate in Nigeria. The study therefore concludes that rising Inflation (INF) significantly increases Under-5 Mortality Rate (UFM) indicating that rising prices may reduce household access to essential healthcare and nutrition for children in Nigeria within the period of study. The study therefore recommended amongst others that Government should initiate and implement effective macroeconomic policies aimed at controlling inflation in order to safeguard household consumption of essential goods and health services, thereby reducing inflation-induced under-five mortality.

Introduction

Health begins at childbirth; and health investment in humans commences at birth (Muthaka, 2013). It has been observed that health occupies an important position in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the United Nations (UN). Specifically, Goal 3 of the SDGs in particular, focused on a considerable reduction in the

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global maternal and child mortality rates and a significant increase in health financing by the year 2030 (WHO, 2016 in Eboh, et al., 2022).

It has been argued that reducing the mortality rate of children is a way of preserving children to grow up to fulfill their potential (Muthaka, 2013). Muthaka further noted that poor health issues such as poor sanitary systems, diarrheal, malnourishment, as well as environmental conditions, among other diseases are linked to higher rates of child mortality.

According to Igberaese & Arodoye (2017), the under-five, as the term connotes, is a child who has not completed five years on earth; that is, the child has only spent between 1 and 59 months on earth. The under-five mortality rate is a vital indicator of the effectiveness of healthcare systems, public health policies and the socio-economic conditions of a population (Kamera & Ijoko, 2025). As noted by McGuire (2006) and Muldoon, et al., (2011), under-five mortality (U5M) is a critical marker of child survival and socio-economic development. However, despite significant global progress, with a 58% reduction in infant mortality and 62% reduction in U5M between 1990 and 2022, there are still nearly five million under-five children's death, which corresponds to an estimated 13,400 deaths every day (UN, 2023).

These deaths, however primarily result from preventable and treatable causes, such as infectious diseases including pneumonia, diarrhea, and malaria, as well as adverse birth outcomes. Thus, nearly 75% of under-five deaths occur among infants (UN, 2022; WHO, 2014). To address this critical issue and make advancements towards reducing under-five mortality and infant mortality rates globally, it is important to have a holistic understanding of the risk factors contributing to these outcomes.

According to Liu et al., (2019) and Romanilik et al., (2020), the degree of population health (infant and under-five mortality rates) is influenced by many factors, such as the economic cycle (GNP), unemployment, income, and other macroeconomic variable. There are also other factors such as education, healthcare expenditures, and even differences in ethnicity that can affect the degree of population health (Islam et al., (2021); Weels et al. (2017); Lorenz et al., (2016).

Thus, it has been observed that inflation, as a key indicator in macro-economics, is closely related to family life, and to a large extent is a global phenomenon (Ciccarelli & Majon, 2010). It has been argued also that rising inflation leads to higher food price, higher cost of living for households, and reduce purchasing power, which in turn have wide spread effects on people's nutrition and health status (UNICEF, 2020); Christian, 2010).

Numerous studies (Kidone & Woldemichael, 2020; Raji, 2020; Hafsa & Roksana, 2023; Usman & Mekonnen, 2024; Jiang & Liu, 2022; Eboh et al., 2022) documented the impact of inflation on children's health. However, the full implication of inflation and under-five mortality in Nigeria is yet to be exposed.

This study investigates the impact of exposure to inflation on under-five mortality in Nigeria. This study is motivated by two important factors. First, Nigeria experienced historically higher levels of inflation for a sustained period between 2010 and 2024. Secondly, Nigeria is one of the sub-Saharan African countries with the highest under-five mortality in the world. It is therefore imperative to understand and quantify how higher inflation exacerbate the prevailing high under-five child mortality rate in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Theoretical Literature Review

Mosley and Chen Theory of Child Survival in Developing Countries

The theoretical basis of this paper like in my previous papers is Mosley and Chen (1984) Theory of Child Survival in Developing Countries. Traditionally, social science research on child mortality has focused on the association between socio-economic status and levels and patterns of mortality in populations. Correlations between mortality and socioeconomic characteristics are used to generate causal inferences about the mortality

determinants. Income and maternal education, for example are two commonly measured correlates (and inferred causal determinants) of child mortality in developing countries population (Mosley & Chen, 1984).

The theory of child survival in developing countries by Mosley and Chen (1984) proposes a new analytical framework for the study of the determinants of child survival in developing countries. The approach incorporates both social and biological variables and integrates research methods employed by social and medical scientists. It also provides for the measurement of morbidity and mortality in a single variable. The framework is based on the premise that all social and economic determinants of child mortality necessarily operate through a common set of biological mechanisms, or proximate determinants, to exert an impact on mortality. The framework according to Mosley & Chen (1984) is intended to advance research on social policy and medical interventions to improve child survival.

The key to the theory is the identification of a set of proximate determinants or intermediate variables that directly influence the risk of morbidity and mortality. All social and economic determinants must operate through these variables to affect child survival. According to Mosely and Chen (1984), the proximate determinants are grouped into five categories:

- i. Maternal factors: age; parity; birth interval
- ii. Environmental contamination: air, food/water/fingers; skin/soil/inanimate objects; insects' vectors
- iii. Nutrient deficiency: calories; protein; micronutrients (vitamins and minerals).
- iv. Injury: accidental; intentional.
- v. Personal illness control: personal preventive measures; medical treatment.

For this study, the theory of child survival is a useful indication that positive improvements in all the proximate determinants will positively affect mortality and morbidity thereby increasing the rate of child survival in Nigeria. A reduction in environmental contamination and personal illness is needed to enhance child survival among under-five children improvement in maternal factors and nutritional deficiency is also needed to balance longevity among under-five children in Nigeria, all things being equal.

Concept of Inflation

Inflation refers to the sustained increase in the general price level of goods and services in an economy over a given period of time. Fernando (2024) in Ezekwu (2025) defined inflation as a gradual loss of purchasing power that is reflected in a broad rise in prices for goods and services over time.

The Concept of Under-Five Mortality

Under-five mortality (U5M) is the probability of a child dying before the fifth birthday, measured per 1,000 live births. According to UNICEF (2025), the under-five mortality rate refers to the probability a new born would die before reaching exactly 5 years of age, expressed per 1,000 live births. According to World Health Organisation (2025), under-five mortality rate is an indicator for SDG 3: "Ensure healthy lives and promote wellbeing for all at all ages". It is also included in the WHO Global reference list of 100 core health indicators.

In 2023, it was noted that 4.8million children under 5 years of age died. This according to UNICEF translates to 13,000 children under the age of 5 dying every day in 2023. Furthermore, globally, infections, diseases, including pneumonia, diarrhea and malaria, remain a leading cause of under-five deaths, along with preterm birth and intra-partum related complications (UNICEF, 2025).

Empirical literature Review

Kidane & Woldmichael (2020) carried out a study on "Does Inflation Kill"? Exposure to food inflation and child mortality. The paper examined the impact of early life exposure to food price inflation on child mortality in Ethiopia. Following survival events since conception, the paper estimated the causal impact of exposure to

inflation during in-utero and infancy. The results show that exposure to a 10 percent inflation in staple food prices during in-utero decreases the survival of children under the age of five by about 5.4 percent.

Raji (2020) studied infant and under-five mortality rates in Nigeria: an impact analysis of macroeconomic conditions. The study investigated the role of macroeconomic conditions on infant and under-five mortality rates in Nigeria for the period 1986 – 2017 using the fully modified OLS techniques. The results show that the unfriendly macroeconomic policy environment such as the instability of inflation rate, unemployment and exchange rate enhanced the increased level of infant and under-five mortality rates in Nigeria.

Usman, Mekennen, Kornher & Braun (2024) studied real consumer food prices and child mortality evidence from low-and-middle-income countries. The paper estimated the effect of short-term changes in real consumer food prices on short-term fluctuations in neonatal, infant, and child mortality rates using a panel dataset covering 59 low-and-middle-income countries (LMICs) for the period 2000 – 2015. The results revealed that rising real food prices had a large and significant effect on neonatal, infant, and child mortalities, regardless of the type of country-specific time trends chosen.

Hafsa & Roksana (2023) studied the impact of food price inflation on child health (infant mortality rate) in Bangladesh: An ARDL approach. The study aims to identify child mortality in Bangladesh as a result of rising food prices from the data of 2000 – 2021. Secondary data collected from WDI was used in the study. Both Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Autoregressive Distributed Lag bound tests were employed as techniques of analysis. The results show that food price inflation, fertility rate has opposing effect on infant mortality in the long run. A 1% upsurge in food price inflation increases the infant mortality by about 0.0009442%; and a 1% increase in fertility rate increases the infant mortality by about 0.0033952%.

Jiang & Liu (2022) studied infant mortality and inflation in China: Based on mixed frequency VAR analysis. The paper investigated the causal relationship between inflation and infant mortality using a mixed frequency vector auto-regressive model (MF-VAR). The findings show that there is a causal relationship between inflation and infant mortality, specifically, that is inflation increases infant mortality.

Woldemichael, Kidane & Shimeles (2017) studied a tax on children? The effects of food price inflation on child health in Ethiopia. Using a rich set of data from Ethiopia that combined high-frequency price data from 119 markets with the Demographic and Health survey, the study estimated the effects of exposure to food price inflation during each month since inception to the 24th month after birth on the physical growth of children aged 6-59 months. The study focused on three staples (teff, wheat and maize). The results show that exposure to food price inflation while in utero and during infancy has detrimental and long-term impacts on children's height and weight.

Usman, Ateeq & Hassan (2025) studied inflation and mortality nexus: empirical evidence from south Asian countries. The paper aimed to analyze the effect of inflation rate on mortality in South Asian countries (like Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka). Data from 1972 to 2018 were collected from world development indicators (WDI), penn world table, and UN comtrade for the selected countries. The dynamic panel model using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) developed by Arellano & Bond (1991) was estimated. The empirical results showed that the rate of inflation, CO₂ emission, population growth, and life expectancy rates have positive and significant impact on mortality rates.

Eboh, Aduku & Onwughalu (2022) studied health expenditure, child mortality and economic growth in Nigeria using time series data covering the 1980-2020 sample periods. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) technique was employed in analyzing the data. Empirical results showed a negative and insignificant impact of government health expenditure on under-five child mortality. The result also showed that government capital expenditure had a negative and insignificant impact on under-five mortality.

Samarawickrama et al. (2025) studied macroeconomic determinants of child mortality in low and lower-middle-income nations. The study examined the impact of macroeconomic factors on child mortality in low-and lower-middle-income countries to formulate policies for those income levels achieve SDG 3.2 by 2030 using panel regression analyses. The findings of the study revealed that in low-income countries women’s employment positively and significantly affects child mortality, while GDP per capita and current health expenditure negatively and significantly affects child mortality.

Akinlo & Odusanya (2016) studied the effects of food prices on under-five and infant mortality rates in sub-Saharan Africa. The paper examined the impact of rising food prices on under-five and infant mortality rates in 31 selected sub-Saharan African countries for the period 2001 – 2012 using the fixed effects, random effects, difference GMM and the system GMM. The results show that rising food prices exert significant adverse effects on both infant and under-five mortality rates in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Methodology

This paper adopted the ex- post facto research design. The choice of ex- post facto was informed by the fact that the numerical data required for the actual empirical analysis was collected from secondary sources.

Model Specification

Under –Five Mortality Model.

This model was adopted from the work of Salatin & Bidari (2014) and Bao, Tao, Afzae & Dorduncu (2022) but with some modifications in terms of the variables.

$$UFM = f(INF, GDPPC, GEH, UNEMP) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

The ordinary least square (OLS) form of the equation is written as:

$$UFM = a_0 + a_1INF + a_2 GDPPC + a_3 GEH + a_4 UNEMP + U \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where; $a_1 > 0$; $a_2 < 0$; $a_3 < 0$, $a_4 > 0$

UFM = under-five mortality rate

INF = Inflation rate

GDPPC = GDP per capita

GEH = Government Expenditure on Health

UNEMP = Unemployment rate

a_0 = Constant

$a_1 - a_4$ = coefficients of explanatory variables

U = error term

Estimation Technique

This study employed descriptive statistics, unit root test, Co-integration, and Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) modelling techniques to estimate the effect of the explanatory variables on the dependent variable. To ensure that the estimated model is robust and unbiased, the fitness of the model was determined by checking goodness of fit statistics and conducting diagnostics tests.

Result and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 below presents the result of the descriptive statistics of the variables employed in the estimations in this study.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics Test Results

	UFM	INF	GDPPC	GEH	UNEMP
Mean	154.9143	18.33257	317609.4	143.2849	14.34000

Median	145.2000	13.01000	226245.0	81.91000	13.90000
Maximum	209.8000	72.84000	1028712.	468.6400	27.40000
Minimum	104.9000	5.390000	5093.070	0.150000	3.500000
Std. Dev.	35.90778	15.66996	308578.0	155.5025	7.699054
Skewness	0.281728	2.200667	0.766491	0.838774	-0.125980
Kurtosis	1.597318	7.021038	2.391439	2.303994	1.681559
Jarque-Bera	3.332293	51.82987	3.967222	4.810445	2.627582
Probability	0.188974	0.000000	0.137572	0.090245	0.268799
Sum	5422.000	641.6400	11116329	5014.970	501.9000
Sum Sq. Dev.	43838.52	8348.623	3.24E+12	822155.3	2015.365
Observations	35	35	35	35	35

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

The result of the descriptive statistics in Tables 1 shows that Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) have a mean value of 154.9143 with a standard deviation of 35.90778. The skewness value of Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) is positive (0.281728), meaning that Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) has a long-right tail while the kurtosis value of Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) is 1.597318 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series are lower than the mean sample.

Inflation (INF) has a mean value of 18.33257 with a standard deviation of 15.66996. The skewness value of Inflation (INF) is negative (2.200667), meaning that Inflation (INF) has a long-left tail while the kurtosis value of Inflation (INF) is 7.021038 (i. e. greater than 3), meaning that it is leptokurtic. That is, it has a peak distribution, meaning that the series has more value higher than the sample mean.

Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a mean value of 317609.4 with a standard deviation of 308578.0. The skewness value of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) is positive (0.766491), meaning that Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a long-right tail while the kurtosis value of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) is 2.391439 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series has low value lower than the sample mean.

Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a mean value of 143.2849 with a standard deviation of 155.5025. The skewness value of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) is positive (0.838774), meaning that Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a long-right tail while the kurtosis value of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) is 2.303994 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series has low value lower than the sample mean.

Unemployment (UNEMP) has a mean value of 14.34000 with a standard deviation of 7.699054. The skewness value of Unemployment (UNEMP) is negative (-0.125980), meaning that Unemployment (UNEMP) has a long-right tail while the kurtosis value of Unemployment (UNEMP) is 1.681559 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series has low value lower than the sample mean.

Again, one important observation in this table is the Jarque-Bera statistics of the variables. It shows that the values of INF is greater than 5.99, meaning that they do not have a normal distribution while UFM, LEXP, MAM, GDPPC, GEH and UNEMP has a value less than 5.99, suggesting that they have a normal distribution.

Based on these observations, it is therefore necessary to test for the stationarity of the variables and the long run relationship since using the variables at level might give a spurious result. The unit root test is conducted so as to make the variables stationary. The study adopts the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test procedure.

Unit Root Test for Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) Model.

Tables 2 below present results of stationarity test for each of variables used using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Results for Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) Model

Variables	ADF at Level	ADF at 1 st Difference	Status	Remarks
UFM	-2.463506	-5.169509	I(1)	Stationary
INF	-2.237259	-4.760123	I(1)	Stationary
GDPPC	1.075593	-7.303771	I(1)	Stationary
GEH	0.326534	-6.316342	I(1)	Stationary
UNEMP	-2.139660	-5.054909	I(1)	Stationary
Critical Values				
1% level	-3.646342	-3.653730		
5% level	-2.954021	-2.957110		
10% level	-2.615817	-2.617434		

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The outcomes of unit root test in Table 2 for the Model, reveals that all the variables were not stationary at level but were stationary at difference. Hence, this study concludes that the variables used in model were integrated of order one, that is I(1). Since the ADF results indicate that the series are of the same order of integration, we proceed to conduct co-integration.

(ii) Co-integration Test Result for Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) Model.

The result of co-integration test for Model one is presented in Table 3 below. This will enable us determine if there exists long run equilibrium relationship among variables applied in this model.

Table 3: Co-integration Test Result for Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) Model.

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.** Critical Value
None *	0.653402	97.19665	69.81889	0.0001
At most 1 *	0.602383	62.23024	47.85613	0.0013
At most 2 *	0.402897	31.79548	29.79707	0.0290
At most 3	0.355000	14.77853	15.49471	0.0639
At most 4	0.009285	0.307839	3.841465	0.5790

Trace test indicates 3 cointegrating equation(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Max-eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.** Critical Value
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None *	0.653402	34.96641	33.87687	0.0370
At most 1 *	0.602383	30.43476	27.58434	0.0209
At most 2	0.402897	17.01695	21.13162	0.1712
At most 3 *	0.355000	14.47069	14.26460	0.0464
At most 4	0.009285	0.307839	3.841465	0.5790

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating equation(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The co-integration outcomes in Table 3 above reveals that the trace test statistics indicate three (3) co-integrating equation at 5 % significance level while the max-eigenvalue statistics indicate two (2) co-integrating equation at 5 % significance level. This suggests that there exists a long-run relationship among variables in the model. Accordingly, the study rejects the null hypothesis of no co-integration amongst the variables but accepts the alternative hypothesis.

(ii) Over-Parameterized ECM Estimation Results for Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) Model.

The result of over-parameterized ECM estimation of the Model is presented in equation 4 below.

Table 4: Over-parameterized ECM Estimation Results for Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) Model.

Dependent Variable: DLOG(UFM)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/29/25 Time: 00:12

Sample (adjusted): 1993 2024

Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.007284	0.006263	-1.162915	0.2619
DLOG(UFM(-1))	1.340659	0.776914	1.725622	0.1037
DLOG(UFM(-2))	-0.811154	0.763663	-1.062189	0.3039
D(INF)	-0.000482	0.000326	-1.478540	0.1587
D(INF(-1))	0.000390	0.000311	1.254291	0.2278
D(INF(-2))	-0.000123	0.000232	-0.528854	0.6042
DLOG(GDPPC)	-0.088608	0.026282	-3.371473	0.0039
DLOG(GDPPC(-1))	0.004203	0.026756	0.157083	0.8771
DLOG(GDPPC(-2))	0.031593	0.026448	1.194519	0.2497
DLOG(GEH)	0.009274	0.005922	1.565961	0.1369
DLOG(GEH(-1))	0.009908	0.005725	1.730507	0.1028
DLOG(GEH(-2))	0.013835	0.005031	2.750159	0.0142
D(UNEMP)	-0.000878	0.000485	-1.809057	0.0893
D(UNEMP(-1))	0.000554	0.000418	1.327785	0.2029
D(UNEMP(-2))	-0.000256	0.000454	-0.564612	0.5802
ECM(-1)	-0.143168	0.078775	-1.817423	0.0879
R-squared	0.743223	Mean dependent var		-0.020498

Adjusted R-squared	0.502495	S.D. dependent var	0.012674
S.E. of regression	0.008940	Akaike info criterion	-6.289767
Sum squared resid	0.001279	Schwarz criterion	-5.556899
Log likelihood	116.6363	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-6.046842
F-statistic	3.087393	Durbin-Watson stat	1.485324
Prob(F-statistic)	0.015897		

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

(iii) Parsimonious ECM of Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) Model.

The result of ECM estimation of the Model is obtainable in table 5 below.

Table 5: Parsimonious ECM Estimation Results for Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) Model.

Dependent Variable: DLOG(UFM)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/29/25 Time: 00:16

Sample (adjusted): 1993 2024

Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.003260	0.005313	-0.613595	0.5458
DLOG(UFM(-1))	0.634496	0.176381	3.597304	0.0016
D(INF)	-0.000181	0.000215	-0.840048	0.4099
D(INF(-1))	0.000636	0.000229	2.773791	0.0111
DLOG(GDPPC)	-0.086764	0.022888	-3.790750	0.0010
DLOG(GDPPC(-2))	-0.043660	0.020880	-2.090956	0.0483
DLOG(GEH(-1))	0.002989	0.002939	1.016877	0.3203
DLOG(GEH(-2))	0.009325	0.003547	2.628984	0.0153
D(UNEMP)	-0.000442	0.000357	-1.238112	0.2287
ECM(-1)	-0.435041	0.160366	-2.712806	0.0108
R-squared	0.678531	Mean dependent var	-0.020498	
Adjusted R-squared	0.547021	S.D. dependent var	0.012674	
S.E. of regression	0.008530	Akaike info criterion	-6.440074	
Sum squared resid	0.001601	Schwarz criterion	-5.982031	
Log likelihood	113.0412	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-6.288246	
F-statistic	5.159536	Durbin-Watson stat	1.788544	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000810			

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

From Table 5 above, it shows that the explanatory variables included in the model explained about 55 percent of variation in Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria as shown by Adjusted-R² of 0.547021. The remaining 45 percent is explained by the error term. The F-statistic of 5.159536 with a prob. Valp-u0ue of

0.000810 shows that the model is statistically significant and that independent variables are significant explanatory factors of the dependent variable. The above implies that model has a goodness of fit and Durbin Watson Statistic of 1.788544 reveals that there is minimal serial autocorrelation among variables used in model. Also, the Error correction coefficient (ECM) is statistically significant and appropriately signed.

Furthermore, From Table 5, the result of the short run estimation shows that Inflation (INF) has a positive (0.000636) relationship with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM), suggesting that percentage increase in Inflation (INF) rate increases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) by 0.000636 units in Nigeria. The positive effect of Inflation (INF) rate on Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) confirms to a priori and therefore is in line with economic theory. The coefficient of Inflation (INF) is statistically significant at 5 percent level in the short run. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Inflation (INF) and Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) but do not reject the alternative hypothesis in the short run. This result is in line with Raji (2020) and Usman et al. (2024).

Both current and past lag 2 of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a negative (-0.086764 and -0.043660, respectively) relationship with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM), suggesting that a unit increase in Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) decreases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria. The negative effect of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) on Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) conforms to a priori and therefore be in line with economic theory. The negative effect of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) on Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) is statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) and Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in the short run but do not reject the alternative hypothesis. This result is in line with Ezekwu & Igwe (2025).

Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a positive (0.009325) relationship with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM), suggesting that a unit increase in Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) increases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) by 0.009325 units in Nigeria. The positive sign of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) on Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) do not confirm to a priori and therefore not line with economic theory. The positive sign of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) on Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) is statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) and Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in the short run but do not reject the alternative hypothesis. This result is contrary to the work of Eboh et al. (2022).

While Unemployment (UNEMP) has a negative (-0.000442) relationship with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM), suggesting that a unit increase in Unemployment (UNEMP) decreases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) by 0.000442 units in Nigeria. The negative sign of Unemployment (UNEMP) on Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) do not confirm to a priori and therefore is not in line with economic theory. The negative sign of Unemployment (UNEMP) on Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Unemployment (UNEMP) and Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in the short run. This result is contrary to the work of Raji (2020).

(v) Post Estimation Test for Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) Model.

The researcher conducted a diagnostic test to determine whether or not series were free from order autocorrelation (Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test) and heteroscedasticity (Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test).

The outcome of the diagnostic tests is presented in Table 6 below

Table 6: Ramsey Reset Test, Serial Correlation LM Test and Homoscedasticity Test Results for Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) Model.

	F-Statistic	Prob. Value
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	0.183128	0.8340
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test	0.236933	0.9800

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

From Table 6, the outcome of autocorrelation test using Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM method showed F-statistics is 0.103337 with a Chi-Square probability value is 0.9022. This indicated that probability value of about 90 percent (0.9022) is larger than 5 percent (0.05) critical value; hence confirmed no serial correlation in model.

Again, result of heteroscedasticity test using Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test showed the F-statistics is 0.363380 and a Chi-Square probability value is 0.9430. This suggested no evidence of heteroskedasticity in model since Chi-square probability value of about 94 percent is more than 5 percent ($p > 0.05$). So, residuals do have constant variance which is desirable in regression denoting that residual are Homoscedastic.

Discussions

Inflation and Under-Five Mortality Rate in Nigeria

The ECM result reveals that Inflation (INF) has a positive relationship with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM). This means that a percentage increase in Inflation (INF) increases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria in the short run within the period under review.

The coefficient of Inflation (INF) is statistically significant with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria within period of study. This means that Inflation (INF) increases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria. The study therefore rejects null hypothesis as there is no significant relationship between Inflation (INF) and Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria but do not reject the alternative hypothesis within period of study. The findings of this study support previous work Raji (2020) and Usman et al. (2024). These scholars have found that inflation weakens public health investments and individual household capacity to care for children, leading to elevated child mortality rates.

GDP per capita and Under-Five Mortality Rate in Nigeria

The study revealed that Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a negative relationship with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM). This means that a unit increase in Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) reduces Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria in the short run within the period under review.

The coefficient of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) is statistically significant at 5 percent with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria. The study therefore rejects null hypothesis as there is no significant relationship between Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) and Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria but do not reject the alternative hypothesis within period of study. This means that Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) significantly reduces Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria.

The findings of this study agree with the work of Samarawickrama et al. (2025) who found that Higher GDP per capita negatively and significantly affect child mortality.

Government Expenditure on Health and Under-Five Mortality Rate in Nigeria

The study reveals that Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a positive relationship with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM). This means that a unit increase in Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) increases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria in the short run within the period under review.

The coefficient of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) is statistically significant at 5 percent with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria within period of study. The study therefore rejects null hypothesis as there is no significant relationship between Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) and Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria but do not reject the alternative hypothesis within period of study. This means that Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) significantly increases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria.

The findings of this study disagree with the work of Samarawickrama et al. (2025) who found that current health expenditure negatively and significantly affects child mortality.

Unemployment and Under-Five Mortality Rate in Nigeria

The study reveals that Unemployment (UNEMP) has a negative relationship with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM). This means that a percentage increase in Unemployment (UNEMP) decreases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria in the short run within the period under review.

The coefficient of Unemployment (UNEMP) is not statistically significant at 5 percent with Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria within period of study. The study therefore accepts null hypothesis as there is no significant relationship between Unemployment (UNEMP) and Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria within period of study. This means that Unemployment (UNEMP) do not have any effect on Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria within the period under review.

The negative findings of this study disagree with the work of Raji (2020) who found that economic downturns with rising unemployment are associated with increased level of infant and under-five mortality rates in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The results of the ECM shows that Inflation (INF) increases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM); GDP per capita (GDPPC) reduces Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM); Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) increases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM); Unemployment (UNEMP) has no significant effect on Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) in Nigeria during the period of study. The study therefore concludes that Inflation (INF) significantly increases Under-Five Mortality Rate (UFM) indicating that rising prices may reduce household access to essential healthcare and nutrition for children in Nigeria within the period of study.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Government are required to initiate and implement effective macroeconomic policies aimed at controlling inflation in order safeguard household consumption of essential goods and health services, thereby reducing inflation-induced under-five mortality.
- ii. Since higher GDP per capita is associated with lower mortality rates reflecting improved living standards and access to healthcare, government should promote investment in diverse economic sectors to raise GDP per capita.
- iii. The government should conduct a comprehensive evaluation of health spending to ensure funds are effectively targeting child health services.

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